

Derek Kennet

From: WhitehouDB <WhitehouDB@cmog.org>
To: 'Derek Kennet' <derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk>
Sent: 13 September 2001 13:22
Subject: RE: Williamson Collection

Dear Dr. Kennet:

Thank you for your message.

I shall be delighted to help you in any way I can. If you have specific questions, please feel free to ask me about them. The general questions you pose would take a great deal of time to answer and, at the end of the day, I imagine you would throw most of the answers away as irrelevant to whatever you are trying to accomplish.

However, I honour Andrew's memory and I will do what I can to help you to honour it, too.

Yours sincerely,

David Whitehouse

-----Original Message-----

From: Derek Kennet [mailto:derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk]
 Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2001 8:08 AM
 To: David Whitehouse
 Subject: Williamson Collection

Dear Dr Whitehouse,

Excuse me for writing to you out of the blue. I am a Research Fellow at Durham. We met once, a few years ago, in Umm al-Qaiwan (in the Beach Hotel with Ernie).

As you may have heard, BIPS have allocated some funds to produce a full catalogue and study of the Williamson Collection. The work will begin in October and will take about one year. Together with a research assistant I plan to create a list and a map (so far as is possible) of all the sites Williamson visited. The Ashmolean pottery collection itself will be catalogued, and we may then attempt some basic distribution analysis etc. We plan to publish the results as a BAR if they are suitable.

I know that you once worked with Williamson. I would be very grateful for any information you may have on him or his work, especially if it might help us to identify sites he visited, or to understand the way he worked. We may include a short chapter on Williamson in the final publication, with a bibliography of his publications and an outline of his brief career. It may be that you also have some information that would help us to compile this.

I look forward to hearing from you. If you would like to know more about what we plan to do, I would be happy to let you know.

Yours

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